

Obtaining the Poynting Continuity Equation from the Lorentz Transformation of an Electric Potential?

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The Poynting continuity equation of electromagnetism: $\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 B \cdot B) + \text{C1 grad dot} (E \times B) = \text{C2 } E \cdot j$ is well-known to follow from Maxwell's em equations.

Here, we wish to start with a charge at rest which creates an energy $q \phi$ with a test charge q . This energy should transfer under a Lorentz transformation and we argue that one may guess the forms: $E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt}$ and $B = \text{grad} \times A$ as being the forces as seen in a moving frame such that $F = qE + q v \times B$. Without knowing Maxwell's equations, we try to argue that one may then obtain the Poynting continuity equation using ϕ' and A' together with the Lorentz gauge $\frac{d\phi'}{dt} \text{partial} (1/c^2) + \text{grad dot} A = 0$ except that $E \cdot j$ is replaced with $E \cdot D'$ Alembertian A .

Charge at Rest and Deducing E and B

In previous notes we have argued that one may deduce E and B in terms of ϕ' and A' by starting with a charge at rest. Such a charge Q creates an electrostatic potential ϕ such that $q\phi$ is the energy felt by a test charge q . This energy should transform as a Lorentz transformation:

$$(0, q\phi) \rightarrow (qA', \phi') \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } A' \text{ is proportional to } v, \text{ the velocity vector}$$

In the rest frame, $E = -\text{grad } \phi$ and force is qE . We suggest that $\text{grad } \phi'$ should also yield a piece of the force as seen in the moving frame. Even though ϕ' is now a function of t as well as position, we do not consider $\frac{d\phi'}{dt} \text{partial}$ as creating a force because we consider $\text{grad } \phi'$ with R as related to the force. This grad may act on retarded time pieces.

If grad acts on ϕ' (called ϕ now for convenience), then one should consider changes in the vector A such as:

$$\text{Grad acting on } A \text{ and } \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial acting on } A. \quad ((2))$$

We wish to have force as a vector multiplied by q , the test charge. It is possible to create a vector from A using $\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial}$ and grad (once) via:

$$\frac{dA}{dt} \text{partial} \text{ and } \text{grad} \times A \quad ((3))$$

If one considers the transformation of $(0, \phi)$ then $A = q v(\text{vector}) \phi$ rest frame. Thus, A is in the direction of v which is fine for $\frac{dA}{dt} \text{partial}$, but $\text{grad} \times A$ would lie on a circle in a plane perpendicular to the motion v . Using $v \times (\text{grad} \times A)$ creates a force inwards like the usual E force. Thus, one may suggest the forces (as seen in the moving frame) to be:

$$E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \text{partial} \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad B = \text{grad} \times A \quad ((4b))$$

We argue that ϕ and A do not need to be obtained from Maxwell's equations necessarily.

It may be shown (see (1)), that work done creating a spherical charge and magnetic are given by:

$$.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E \quad \text{and} \quad .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B \quad ((5))$$

These relationships depend only on the idea of force being $F = qE + q \times vB$. (One may also use ϕ and A).

We ask: Is it possible to obtain a relationship for this energy, i.e. the Poynting continuity equation, without using Maxwell's em equations?

Obtaining the Poynting Continuity Equation Using ϕ and A ?

The Poynting continuity equation is given by:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } \{ .5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B \} + C_1 \text{ grad dot } (ExB) = C_2 E \cdot j \quad ((6))$$

Here j is current density. We note that $c=1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$ and set $c=1$. Thus, we do not worry about ϵ_0 , μ_0 or C_1 , C_2 . (One may check (1) for exact values of C_1 , C_2 and $c=1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$). We set $c=1$.

Our objective is to use the expressions ((4a)) and ((4b)) to prove the Poynting continuity equation. We argue that this implies that one could create a continuity equation for the work ((5)) based on the forms of E and B in terms of A and ϕ . In order to do so, we note that one may introduce the Lorentz gauge:

$$d/dt \phi + \text{grad dot } A = 0 \quad c=1 \quad ((7))$$

An explanation of the Lorentz gauge is given in (2) and it is basically a relationship which is consistent with ((4a)) and ((4b)).

Secondly, we make use of:

$$\text{Sum } i,j \text{ (term symmetric in the interchange of } i,j) \text{ (term antisymmetric in } i,j) = 0$$

Given the energy form ((5)), we calculate $d/dt \text{ partial}$ of this term directly, expressing E and B in terms of A and ϕ . For a continuity equation one expects: grad dot vector . This vector must contain E and B and must bring in a proper kind of symmetry for ϕ and A derivative terms. Given $E \cdot E$ and $B \cdot B$ forms we consider ExB as the vector. $E+B$ does not work because it is not quadratic in fields. We only wish to use E and B to create the vector. We thus see if $d/dt \text{ partial energy density}$ matches $\text{grad dot } (ExB)$ when E and B are expressed in terms of A and ϕ , because we assume that Maxwell's em equations are not available. We use dtA as $dA/dt \text{ partial}$.

$\frac{1}{2} E \cdot E = \frac{1}{2} \{ \text{grad } \phi \cdot \text{grad } \phi + \dot{A} \cdot \dot{A} + 2 \text{grad } \phi \cdot \dot{A} \}$ ((8)) and

$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } \frac{1}{2} E \cdot E = \text{grad } \phi \cdot \text{grad } \dot{\phi} + \dot{A} \cdot \dot{\dot{A}} + \text{grad } \dot{\phi} \cdot \dot{A} + \text{grad } \phi \cdot \dot{\dot{A}}$ ((9))

Note: there is summation implied if one sees the same index twice.

$B \cdot B = \epsilon_{ijk} \dot{A}_k \epsilon_{ilm} \dot{A}_l = \{ \dot{A}_k \dot{A}_k - \dot{A}_k \dot{A}_j \}$ ((10))

$\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } B = \frac{1}{2} \dot{A}_k \{ \dot{A}_k - \dot{A}_j \} + \frac{1}{2} \dot{A}_k \{ \dot{A}_k - \dot{A}_j \} = \dot{A}_k (\dot{A}_k - \dot{A}_j)$ ((11))

$E \cdot B = \epsilon_{ijk} (-\dot{\phi}_i - \dot{A}_j) \epsilon_{klm} \dot{A}_m = -\dot{\phi}_i \dot{A}_j + \dot{\phi}_i \dot{A}_j - \dot{A}_j \dot{A}_k + \dot{A}_j \dot{A}_k$ ((12))

$\text{Grad } \cdot (E \cdot B) = \text{div } \dot{\phi} \{ \dot{A}_j - \dot{A}_i \} - \text{div } \dot{\phi} \{ \dot{A}_j + \dot{A}_i \} - (\dot{A}_j \dot{A}_k) \{ \dot{A}_j - \dot{A}_i \}$
 $- \dot{A}_j \{ \dot{A}_j - \dot{A}_i \}$ ((13))

At this point we wish to do three things:

- ((A)) look for sum i,j symmetric(i,j) antisymmetric(i,j) because this yields 0
- ((B)) look for a D'Alembertian of A.
- ((C)) use the Lorentz gauge $\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } \phi + \text{grad } \cdot A = 0$

In terms of symmetry-antisymmetry, the first term of $\text{grad } \cdot (E \cdot B)$, $\text{div } \dot{\phi} \{ \dot{A}_j - \dot{A}_i \}$, yields 0.

In terms of symmetry-antisymmetry $\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} B \cdot B$ added to $-(\dot{A}_j \dot{A}_k) \{ \dot{A}_j - \dot{A}_i \}$, the third term from $\text{grad } \cdot (E \cdot B)$ creates a $\text{Sum } i,j$ symmetric(ij) antisymmetric(ij) = 0.

The last term from $\text{grad } \cdot (E \cdot B)$ yields a piece: $-\dot{A}_j \text{div } \dot{A}_i$.

If this is combined with $\text{grad } \dot{\phi} \cdot \text{grad } \phi$ from $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{1}{2} E \cdot E$, this cancels due to the Lorentz gauge. The piece $-\dot{A}_j \text{div } \dot{A}_i$ will become part of a D'Alembertian.

A piece from the second term of $\text{grad } \cdot (E \cdot B)$, namely $-\dot{\phi}_i (\dot{A}_j + \dot{A}_i)$ combines with $\text{grad } \dot{\phi} \cdot \text{grad } \phi$ from $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{1}{2} E \cdot E$ and cancels due to the Lorentz gauge. Another piece, $-\dot{\phi}_i \dot{A}_j$ remains, but this is linked to a D'Alembertian.

If one examines $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{1}{2} E \cdot E$, the second and fourth terms are linked to a D'Alembertian, i.e. contain $\dot{A} \cdot \dot{A}$. The first and third terms have already canceled out due to the Lorentz gauge with a piece of $\text{grad } \cdot (E \cdot B)$.

Thus, all that remain are pieces of the D'Alembertian of A, i.e.:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (.5 E \text{ dot } E + .5 B \text{ dot } B) + \text{Grad dot} (ExB) = E \text{ dot } D'Alembertian \text{ of } A \quad ((14))$$

If D'Alembertian of A is proportional to j, the current density (i.e qv for a single charge Q moving in the x direction) and Power= F dot v, then $v \text{ dot} (Q E + Q vxB) = QE \text{ dot } v$. Thus:

$$D'Alembertian \text{ of } A = \text{constant } j \text{ where } j \text{ is current density} \quad ((15))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we first argue that given an electrostatic potential phi for a charge Q, and the idea that $F = -q \text{ grad } \phi$ where q is a test charge with energy = qphi, one may Lorentz transform (0, qphi) into (qA'c, q phi'). Applying derivatives to try to find force as seen in the moving frame, we suggest one may deduce: $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt \text{ partial}$ and $B = \text{grad } \times A$ such that $F = qE + qvxB$. If one knows force, it is possible to show that electric work is $.5 \epsilon_0 E \text{ dot } E$ and magnetic, $.5/\mu_0 B \text{ dot } B$. If one wishes to create a continuity equation using $d/dt \text{ partial} (.5\epsilon_0 E \text{ dot } E + .5/\mu_0 B \text{ dot } B) + \text{grad dot vector} = \text{something}$, one may try $\text{grad dot} (ExB)$ (for its symmetry features) and use the explicit forms of E and B using phi and A. If one uses the Lorentz gauge $d\phi/dt \text{ partial} (1/cc) + \text{grad dot } A=0$, one may obtain the Poynting continuity equation without making use of Maxwell's em equations. This gives a continuity equation in terms of a D'Alembertian of A which is equivalent to $\text{power}=F \text{ dot } v = E \text{ dot } j$ where j is current density, i.e. Qv for a particle with charge Q moving in one direction with velocity v.

References

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